

Growth Prospects of Women Run Home-Based Businesses: A Study of Home Chefs

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Abstract: The COVID pandemic caused disruption to the restaurant industry. Businesses for home-cooked food experienced traction. Food being a skill domain of women, many women entered the market, and the ones already in the market expanded their business. Closing down of restaurants during the lockdown period led to consumers substituting their demand for outside food in favor of home chefs. That might be a trigger point but not the sole factor for the success of many home chefs. This exploratory study tries to identify factors playing role in the success of the home chef business. Qualitative research methodology is adopted with 11 in-depth interviews of growing home chefs of Ahmedabad city. With content analysis, five sets of factors are identified.

Keywords: Home Based Business, Home Chef, Women Entrepreneurs

1. Introduction

Amidst reducing female labour force participation, women entrepreneurs are increasing their presence in India. Self-employment /entrepreneurship seems to be offering good opportunities to fill the void of poor availability of jobs or poor wages against their qualification. There are 432 million working-age women and 13.5 –15.7 million women-owned businesses in India, which is about 3 percent ¹. The Sixth Economic Census shows that 90% of women entrepreneurs run microenterprises and about 79% have to self-finance their businesses. A sizable proportion of this group is operating from home. Post-pandemic the preference to operate from work has significantly increased. Women prefer pink-collar ventures even though they are highly competitive and less remunerative. ILO finds that 28 percent of urban Indian women are willing to accept work at home (ILO: 2009).

During the market disruption caused by the pandemic, one sector gained traction - that is home kitchen providing delivery of home-cooked food. This is a home-based business (HBB) involving a large number of women. Since the pandemic, due to changes in socio-economic factors and increased focus on health, people are wary of outside food and the concept of home chefs is gaining popularity. Home chefs serve home-cooked meals using natural spices and herbs and good quality ingredients often having higher nutritional value. This makes the food more flavourful and healthier as compared to restaurant food. Due to

¹<https://www.ibef.org/blogs/women-entrepreneurs-shaping-the-future-of-india>

this, the specific customers are preferring hygienic home-cooked food over the restaurant and packaged food.

This paper is a part of a larger study focusing to understand the changed business structure of the outside food industry after the pandemic. The objective of this paper is to explore underlying factors that have made the Home-Chef business successful. It is based on in-depth interviews of 11 women home chefs of Ahmedabad that have grown in the last two years and are intending to grow further. The universality of the findings of this study will be tested in subsequent research.

2. Literature Review

HBB is defined as any business entity that sells products or services and is run by a self-employed person, with or without workers, who utilizes their home as a base to manage their business (Mason, et al, 2011). As employees or business owners working at home, women are more likely to be involved than men (Danhauser, 1999). HBB provides females with an alternative option of employment having a better work-life balance and lifestyle flexibility (Walker et al., 2008, Furry, 1992; Priestnitz, 1989). The main attraction to starting a home-based business is the low-cost investment required for home businesses. By utilizing personal savings, the authority to make business decisions lies with the owner and therefore the controlling growth and development of the business (Bin Dahari, et al., 2019).

The literature on women-owned HBBs has identified several factors that affect the survival and growth of these businesses. Some factors to influence growth and success in small businesses are knowledge and skills, performance, technology, owner attitude, motivation, finances and capital, and creativity (Purateera, et, al, 2009). HBB also provides self-satisfaction in delivering a product/ service while having flexibility and freedom of expressing creativity. More than the gratification of wealth creation it is the sense of accomplishment, recognition, and pride that comes from doing the job (Walker and Brown 2004).

The landscape of women-owned small businesses and HBBs has shifted dramatically in the last ten years as a result of advances in ICT and changes in economic, social, and lifestyle factors. As a result, many of the early concepts used to describe women-owned business growth, success, and expansion may no longer be applicable. In support of this point, McGregor and Tweed (2002) showed that 'networked women' who are better educated and affiliated will seek expansion more as compared to other female or male entrepreneurs. This is contradictory to the literature which suggests that women are less growth driven and do business to only satisfy their intrinsic needs.

Although male and female entrepreneurs are equally likely to desire growth, there are differences in how they wish to expand (Cliff, 1998). She suggested female entrepreneurs usually set their threshold for business expansion, beyond which they would not prefer to. This threshold is the size that enables control of the business and allows a balance of work and personal life (Cliff, 1998). This meant in the case of female entrepreneurs personal considerations overpowered the economic consideration when taking business expansion decisions. Powell and Eddleston (2008) suggested female business owners placed less value on achieving business success than their male counterparts. The study is to identify factors contributing to the growth of home chefs. These factors are to be tested for their universalities in subsequent research.

3. Methodology

A qualitative content analysis approach was employed to gain a better and deeper understanding of factors affecting the growth of home chefs, their experiences, and aspirations. The participants were selected because they have grown beyond the category of a hobby. In qualitative studies, Interviews are considered complete when the data gets saturated. That is, when data gets repeated and no new information is obtained from new interviews, the sampling process is considered to be complete (Patton, 1990). Data saturation occurred after 11 interviews. To gather the relevant information, semi-structured, in-depth interviews were conducted with each participant. The study's objectives were conveyed to participants before each interview. The interview questions were from reasons for beginning a business to motivation, challenge, the impact of the environment, and the variables contributing to their business's success. Before the meeting, interview questions were sent to each participant so that they were informed about the content of the interview and could evaluate the time required to respond to the interview questions. At the time of the interview, permission was taken to allow the interviewer to record the interview and the participants were assured of the confidentiality of their personal information.

The interview time varied from 35 to 90 minutes, depending on the experience and the information shared by the participant. For the content analysis, meaning units were determined and then related codes were extracted. The similarities and differences between initial codes were observed and then categorized into broader themes based on similarity (Graneheim and Lundman, 2004).

3.1. Socio-Economic and Entrepreneurial Profile of the respondents

The socio-economic background and entrepreneurial profile of the respondents give an insight into understanding the nature and structure of the business.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile

Age		Annual Family Income	
>40	9	<10 lakh	6
30-40	1	10 - 25 Lakh	2
<30	1	>25 Lakh	2
Education		Type of House	
Graduation	4	Flats	7
Post-Graduation	7	Bungalow	3
Entrepreneurial Profile			
Years into the Venture		Planning Expansion	
>1 year	3	Planning a Restaurant	4
1 to 2	5	Planning a Cloud Kitchen	2
>2 years	3	Expansion of Scale	3
Planning for the Venture		Not Sure	2
> 6 months	3	Have License	
3 to 6 months	1	Yes	9
<3 Months	3	No	2
No Planning	4		

The socio-economic profile of the sample is broadly homogeneous. Most of them are above 40 years old, educated, and married with children. They belong to middle-class families where theirs is not the primary source of income. They live in either bungalows or flats - a majority of which are gated townships. This background gives them the advantage to connect with a large number of friends, family, and neighbours with higher spending capacity, who are health conscious and do not mind paying for the quality product. They are into the business for some time, have obtained a license to operate, and are planning for expansion in a different format

4. Results

Interviews of 11 home chefs were focused on their journey so far and factors they perceived to be important. After categorization and integration of results, five main themes were obtained (table 2)

Table 2: Themes and Sub-Themes

	Themes	Sub-Themes
1	Motivation	Passion for Cooking
		Recognition
		Social Cause
2	Family	Encouragement
		Work sharing

Table 2 continued

3	Market	Closing of Restaurants
		Preference for Healthy Food
		Trends for Regional Cuisines
		Willingness to pay
		Convenience
4	Technology	Digital Marketing
		Innovation and Upskilling
		Online delivery portals
5	Support Groups in the ecosystem	Networking
		Handholding
		Guiding

4.1. Motivation

The high motivation level of an entrepreneur is a prerequisite for the growth of the business. All participants are motivated to continue and expand their ventures.

Passion for Cooking: They are into this business for their passion for cooking, the skill and art they learned from mother, sister, or any other family member

Hemini: My mother used to involve me and my sister in cooking dinner for the family since I was 10. She was a much-admired cook in the family. I continued her legacy after my marriage.

Recognition: Respondents mentioned that admiration from their customers is a very important factor motivating them.

Kiran: No matter whose daughter and wife I am, my food has given me a true identity. I do not want to lose this identity

Social Cause: Earning some money is not the only objective to be in this business for many. They either want to prompt regional cuisine and/or want to work towards forming healthy eating habits.

Hemini: I make traditional sweets because this generation has grown up eating cakes and chocolates. I want them to connect with our culture with traditional sweets.

4.2. Family

Operations from home are a necessary aspect of the business model discussed here. It was not possible to run a business without the support of family members.

Encouragement: Most women are encouraged by their kids, husbands, and in one case mother-in-law.

Hemini: My husband and parents were after me to start something of my own after my daughter was born.

Work-sharing: Eight respondents of eleven said that their family members help them when a large order is to be delivered.

Bhavana: My daughter often helps me with packaging. My husband would manage delivery when I am too occupied. Family members extending help not only help in cutting the cost but also strengthen the family ties.

4.3. Market Forces

All participants mentioned that the market for outside food has changed significantly, especially after COVID.

Closing of restaurants: The business of home chefs boomed when restaurants were closed due to the lockdown.

Kiran: My business was at its peak during the lockdown **Preference for Healthy Food:** Participants have observed a trend toward healthy food that gained traction post COVID

Bhavana: People are becoming health conscious. Even in the outside food, they ensure quality.

Trends for Regional Cuisine: The respondents have noted a growing trend toward experimenting with traditional regional food.

Bhavna: There is a growing awareness of the diverse traditions of our country. So, people want to experiment with regional cuisines.

Willingness to Pay: There is a growing consumer segment who is ready to pay high prices for healthy food. They prefer home chefs even if their prices are higher than the market.

Shimul: People would pay for health and hygiene. Nobody wants to compromise with health.

Convenience: Demand for outside food is growing because it offers a convenient option to families where husband and wife both are working.

Mridu: Many of my clients are working couples. They order from me often whenever they don't have time. They get home-cooked food from me whenever they don't have time. So, there is no guilt in eating outside food.

4.4. Technology

The growth of ICT in recent years has contributed a lot to the growth of the home chef business.

Digital Marketing: Internet penetration has made it easier to contact the target segments. Traditional media is rarely used by homechefs. Social media posts and reels are the major way to do marketing. The existing customers are regularly posted with new menu items on WhatsApp, Facebook, or Instagram.

Reena: There is no need to spend money on marketing. Instagram helps me to regularly post pics of my dishes. My USP is my presentation and people order by looking at the pictures only.

Innovation and up-skilling: The home chefs also need to regularly innovate their cuisine or explore cuisines to the demand of customers. They learn different types of cuisines, their presentation, etc, through internet sources. Many of them who were not active on social media started to learn about developing the content and its marketing from sources available on google. They also attended online workshops and seminars for upskilling their culinary skills.

Santosh: Knew nothing about posting reels on Instagram. My sons initially helped me, but now I can regularly post on my own.

Online delivery Portals: The customers used to pick up the order or it was delivered by these home chefs earlier to the nearby areas. This limited the area in which homechefs used to operate. But now with the entry of online delivery portals, the home chefs can deliver the order to faraway places also and thus can geographically expand their business. 9 out of the 11 homechefs were using online portals.

Shimul: I can deliver to distant places, thanks to Swiggy Food delivery. Earlier I was declining those orders.

4.5. Support Groups in the ecosystem

There is a significant contribution of the support groups existing in the present ecosystem of the food industry of Ahmedabad. All the respondents are members of the Food Entrepreneurs Alliance (FEA). They acknowledge multiple roles played by the support groups

Networking: Being a member of a group brings them in contact with peers. Businesses grow with each other's recommendations.

Kavita: I will give huge credit to FEA and its mentors for what I am today. I got to know so many people at their events or through the WhatsApp group. It helped me immensely in expanding my business network.

Handholding: A support group like FEA does the work of mentoring. All agreed that there is always someone to answer a query by any of the members.

Divya: Mentors of FEA recommended my name to many restaurants for designing their menus. Now, along with business I am specializing in designing regional cuisine menus.

Guiding: Members of FEA always get appropriate guidance from the group, which is very essential for a new entrepreneur.

Apra: There is always an answer to queries regarding the recipe, using the right ingredients, sources of material, cost-effective sources, eco-friendly practices, government norms, etc.

5. Conclusion

The Home Chef business got traction after COVID due to a strong change in preference among the consumer for home-cooked food. Many entered the market during the lockdown and withered away soon after, but a few sustained and are expanding. These successful women belong to the upper middle-income segment, networking with the consumers having high paying capacity. These educated women have found employment that breeds their skills and creativity without requiring any borrowed capital. Businesses of home chefs boomed due to growing demand, use of ICT, and support from friends, families, and support groups like FEA. These contributing factors to the growing need to be tested with a larger number of home chefs to check their universality.

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